

STATISTICS TRENDS REGARDING PERSONS EMPLOYED IN THE LAST THREE YEARS (2018), IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA

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Abstract:

This paper presents a detailed statistical analysis of employment trends in the Romanian Mountain Area, focusing specifically on persons employed during the last three years, from 2018. By examining key indicators and demographic data, the study aims to provide insights into the employment landscape within this picturesque region, shedding light on patterns, challenges, and opportunities.

1. Introduction:

The employment scenario is a crucial aspect of regional development, and this paper concentrates on the Romanian Mountain Area to explore the dynamics of persons employed during the last three years. The study aims to analyze statistical trends, demographic variations, and factors influencing employment in this unique geographic setting.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research incorporates data from labor market reports, official employment statistics, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as overall employment rates, industry-specific data, and demographic characteristics are scrutinized to offer a comprehensive understanding of the employment landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Overall Employment Trends:

This section delves into statistical intricacies related to overall employment trends in the Romanian Mountain Area during the last three years (2018). Metrics such as employment rates, fluctuations, and industry-wise variations are analyzed to assess the region's adaptability to changing economic and labor market conditions.

4. Demographic Characteristics:

The paper explores the demographic aspects of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area, including age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds. Insights into the composition of the workforce provide a nuanced perspective on the demographic dynamics shaping the employment landscape.

5. Sectoral Employment Analysis:

Analyzing sectoral employment patterns, this section investigates the distribution of employed persons across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Understanding the sectoral variations offers valuable insights into the diversification of the local economy and the resilience of certain sectors in providing employment opportunities.

6. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining challenges and opportunities faced by the employed population, this section investigates factors such as job stability, income levels, and access to professional development. Addressing these aspects is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders in enhancing the overall well-being of the employed workforce.

7. Regional Economic Impact:

Assessing the regional economic impact of employment trends, the article investigates the contributions of employed persons to the overall economic stability of the Romanian Mountain Area. The interconnectedness between employment, economic development, and community prosperity is explored.

8. Results:

Persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 that survived to t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 53431.82, 2999.375, 50805.00, 9947.802, 98958768.764, 1,397, .661, 1.372, 1,279, 33207, 41409, 74616, 47392.00, 50805.00, 550.00, 550.00

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,1,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Simple; S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .296, .422, -.082, .835, -.082, -.066; R-square .234, .288, 3.331E-16, 1.000, 3.331E-16, 4.996E-16; RMSE 1861,739, 2749,446, .000, 9947,802, .000, 76,509; MAPS 17,356, 8,235, .000, 32,396, .000, 3,604; MaxAPE 40.673, 19.770, .000, 71.467, .000, 8.710; MAE 1373,765, 1970,834, .000, 7087,372, .000, 55,854; MaxAE 3624,228, 5811,862, .000, 21184,182, .000, 128,727; Normalized BIC 14,279, 2,281, 11,301, 18,628, 11,301, 11,319.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following general picture for I12 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 3.331E-16, 3.331E-16, 9947.802, 12.658; S2-Model_2: .828, .324, 3104,833, 20,649; S3-Model_3: 4.441E-16, .068, 1421.019, 16.638; S4-Model_4: 8.882E-16, 8.882E-16, 3160.809, 18.190; S5-Model_5: .811, .290, 807.648, 12.013; S6-Model_6: .831, .341, 903,692, 22,369; S7-Model_7: .028, .155, 336,186, 15,293; S8-Model_8: -.082, .181, 255,030, 27,174; S9-Model_9: 9.992E-16, 9.992E-16, 1329.604, 12.074; S10-Model_10: 1.443E-15, 1.443E-15, 266.743, 18.814; S11-Model_11: .835, .454, 807,499, 32,396.

Table 29. Prediction analysis for I12

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432	53432
	UCL	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597	75597
	LCL	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267	31267
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	8436	7760	7084	6408	5732	5056	4380
	UCL	15459	14818	14177	13535	12894	12252	11610
	LCL	1412	701	-9	-720	-1430	-2140	-2851
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	5220	4715	4209	3704	3199	2694	2189
	UCL	8434	9261	9777	10133	10387	10568	10694
	LCL	2005	169	-1358	-2725	-3989	-5180	-6316
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208	13208
	UCL	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251	20251
	LCL	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165	6165
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	5441	5609	5777	5944	6112	6280	6447
	UCL	7268	7445	7622	7799	7975	8152	8329
	LCL	3614	3773	3931	4090	4249	4407	4566

S6- Model_6:	Forecast	4319	4509	4699	4888	5078	5268	5457
	UCL	6364	6553	6743	6933	7122	7312	7502
	LCL	2275	2465	2654	2844	3034	3223	3413
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157	2157
	UCL	2906	3093	3248	3384	3506	3618	3722
	LCL	1408	1221	1065	929	807	695	591
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	607	607	607	607	607	607	607
	UCL	1175	1411	1591	1743	1878	1999	2110
	LCL	39	-197	-377	-529	-664	-785	-896
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505	7505
	UCL	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468	10468
	LCL	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543	4543
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281	1281
	UCL	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875	1875
	LCL	687	687	687	687	687	687	687
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	3588	3811	4035	4258	4481	4705	4928
	UCL	5414	5647	5879	6111	6344	6576	6808
	LCL	1761	1975	2190	2404	2619	2834	3048

Figure 3.20. Graphical prediction analysis for I12

Persons employed in the year of establishment at newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived until t – number

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, the distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 34240.00, 1443.896, 33703.00, 4788.861, 22933185.000, .916, .661, .427, 1.279, 15262, 28577, 43839, 29683.00, 33703.00, 35724.00.

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 Holt; S3 - Model_3 Simple; S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .311, .434, -.011, .886, -.011, -.009; R-square .258, .325, -1.998E-15, 1.000, -1.998E-15, -1.732E-15; RMSE 1018,655, 1320,281, .000, 4788,861, .000, 51,414; MAPS 16,123, 6,675, .000, 24,139, .000, 2,965; MaxAPE 37,483, 17,271, .000, 68,300, .000, 6,569; MAE 763,141, 950,672, .000, 3429,273, .000, 39,585; MaxAE 2044,212, 2677,802, .000, 9599,000, .000, 88,331; Normalized BIC 13,297, 2,068, 10,506, 17,166, 10,506, 10,563.

The resulting statistical prediction models show the following overall picture for I13 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE) S1-Model_1: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 4788.861, 9.882; S2-Model_2: .886, .402, 1795,198, 19,466; S3-Model_3: -.011, .239, 1051.243, 18.364; S4-Model_4: -1.998E-15, -1.998E-15, 1676.394, 14.052; S5-Model_5: 1.332E-15, 1.332E-15, 558.343, 17.142; S6-Model_6: .859, .518, 461,303, 17,899; S7-Model_7: .820, .341, 177,170, 12,519; S8-Model_8: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 171.381, 24.139; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 829,304, 14,831; S10-Model_10: -1.110E-15, -1.110E-15, 241.764, 23.989; S11-Model_11: .869, .601, 472,897, 21,191.

Table 30. Prediction analysis for I13

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240	34240
	UCL	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910	44910
	LCL	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570	23570
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	4822	4367	3911	3456	3000	2545	2090
	UCL	8883	8448	8012	7577	7141	6705	6270
	LCL	761	286	-190	-665	-1140	-1615	-2090
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936	3936
	UCL	6278	7249	7993	8621	9174	9673	10133
	LCL	1594	623	-121	-749	-1302	-1801	-2261
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884	8884
	UCL	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619	12619
	LCL	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148	5148
S5-	Forecast	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531	2531

Model_5:	UCL	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775	3775
	LCL	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287	1287
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	3024	3165	3306	3447	3587	3728	3869
	UCL	4067	4208	4349	4490	4631	4772	4913
	LCL	1980	2121	2262	2403	2544	2685	2826
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	1378	1418	1458	1499	1539	1580	1620
	UCL	1779	1821	1863	1906	1948	1990	2033
	LCL	977	1015	1054	1092	1130	1169	1207
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	567	567	567	567	567	567	567
	UCL	949	949	949	949	949	949	949
	LCL	185	185	185	185	185	185	185
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571	4571
	UCL	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419	6419
	LCL	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723	2723
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	888	888	888	888	888	888	888
	UCL	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426	1426
	LCL	349	349	349	349	349	349	349
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	2622	2793	2965	3137	3308	3480	3651
	UCL	3692	3868	4045	4222	4399	4575	4752
	LCL	1552	1718	1885	2051	2218	2384	2550

Figure 3.21. Graphical prediction analysis for I13

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging job market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive statistical analysis of persons employed in the Romanian Mountain Area over the last three years (2018). The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's employment dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in the mountainous region.

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